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THE RIGHT TO OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH, SAFETY AND DIGNITY – EU WORKERS’ FUNDAMENTAL RIGHT VIEWED FROM CROATIAN PERSPECTIVE

Abstract:

This paper has two objectives. Firstly, to warn that the workers’ right to occupational health, safety and dignity is the fundamental right defined in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, because this fact is together with its legal implications disregarded in Croatia. The right is exercised based on the applicable EU Directives and the European Social Charter (revised). Obligation and responsibility of Croatia as a member state is to fully and properly transpose all requirements defined in European sources into the national legal framework, and as a result the second objective of the paper is to assess the legislative achievements of Croatia.

The paper brings the analysis and comparison of selected normative solutions from the sources of European and national legislation relevant for this topic, and legal interpretations of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia. The results show that there are obstacles to the efficient exercise of the fundamental workers’ right to occupational health, safety and dignity in Croatia. They include deficient regulations that do not entirely reflect the intentions of EU legislators and the judicial practice when it departs from the regulations in which the normative content of rights and duties of subjects in labour relations is entirely appropriately defined in relation to EU legislation.

Key words: *occupational safety and health, dignity at work, harassment, special working conditions, termination of the employment contract*

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I. INTRODUCTION

From the perspective of workers and unions in Croatia, the right to pay and other benefits belongs to the most important labour-related rights. The actors of collective labour relations devote much more attention to them than to the rights of workers and obligations of employers connected with occupational health, safety and dignity. This conclusion arises from the insight into selected collective agreements.¹ However, whether the worker will be in the situation to work and earn his or her pay and thus enjoy other material rights depends solely on his or her working ability (health status and psychological fitness). Working ability is directly under the influence of the way in which an employer treats the obligations concerning the implementation of the protection of safety, health and dignity at work. It is therefore both justified and important to put under notice that the right to this kind of protection is the fundamental right of workers in the EU and that this fact must guide the design of the normative content and the realization of that right in Croatia.

Given that Croatia is a member state of the EU, the paper outlines the sources of EU legislation, which are superordinate to Croatian legal order and define the right to occupational health, safety and dignity as the fundamental workers' right. EU legal sources set minimum normative content to be transposed to the legal orders of the member states. After that, the paper summarizes the normative content of that legislation as it is established in the Croatian legal order. Finally, prior to the conclusion, there are three examples taken from the regulations and court practice in Croatia that lead to the conclusion that legal order and court practice in Croatia still deviate from EU normative content and legal interpretations, unfortunately to the detriment of workers.

II. NORMATIVE CONTENT OF THE WORKERS' RIGHT TO OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH, SAFETY AND DIGNITY

2.1. EU legal framework

The right to occupational safety, health and dignity is unquestionably the fundamental workers' right in the EU, because it follows from the provisions of Article 31 (Fair and just

¹ Kolektivni ugovor zadjelatnost humanitarnog razminiravanja, *eng.* Collective agreement for the humanitarian mine clearing (Official Gazette 66/14); Kolektivni ugovor za djelatnost privatnog zdravstva Hrvatske, *eng.* Collective agreement for the private health care sector in Croatia (Official Gazette 150/14); Kolektivni ugovor za HEP grupu, *eng.* Collective agreement for the HEP company (Official Gazette 132/14); Kolektivni ugovor za Hrvatsku lutriju d.o.o., *eng.* Collective agreement for the Croatian Lottery Ltd. (Official Gazette 133/14); Kolektivni ugovor za zaposlenike u srednjoškolskim ustanovama, *eng.* Collective agreement for the secondary schools' employees (Official Gazette 72/14) and Kolektivni ugovor ugostiteljstva, *eng.* Collective agreement for the catering industry (Official Gazette 16/15).

working conditions) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union². Every worker in the EU has the right to working conditions which respect his or her health, safety and dignity and every worker has the right to limitation of maximum working hours, to daily and weekly rest periods and to an annual period of paid leave. The Charter has the same legal force as the establishing treaties.³ With respect to the normative content of the said right, it is important to point out two circumstances. First, issues relating to the organization of working hours present special measures of safety at work. They do not pertain to the rights and obligations primarily or exclusively aimed at regulating the labour market supply and demand. Second, the Charter treats the protection of workers' dignity as directly connected to the protection of health and safety at work and they both are important integral parts of working conditions.

Other provisions of the Charter also contribute to the normative content of the right to occupational safety, health and dignity of every worker in the EU. "Young people admitted to work must have working conditions appropriate to their age and be protected against economic exploitation and any work likely to harm their safety, health or physical, mental, moral or social development or to interfere with their education."⁴ "EU recognizes and respects the entitlement to social security benefits and social services providing protection in cases such as maternity or industrial accidents, in accordance with the rules laid down by EU law and national laws and practices."⁵

In accordance with the Preamble of the Charter⁶ the Explanations Relating to the Charter should be taken into consideration as well⁷. They point to the conclusion that the

² Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (OJ C 83)

³ Article 6 of the Treaty on European Union (consolidated version 2012) (OJ C 326)

⁴ Ibid. Article 32 (Prohibition of child labour and protection of young people at work)

⁵ Ibid. Article 34 (Social security and social assistance)

⁶ '... the Charter will be interpreted by the courts of the Union and the Member States with due regard to the explanations prepared under the authority of the Praesidium of the Convention which drafted the Charter and updated under the responsibility of the Praesidium of the European Convention.'

⁷ Explanations Relating to the Charter of Fundamental Rights (OJ C 303, 14. 12. 2007.)

Explanation on Article 31 (Fair and just working conditions):

'1. Paragraph 1 of this Article is based on Directive 89/391/EEC on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work. It also draws on Article 3 of the Social Charter and point 19 of the Community Charter on the rights of workers, and, as regards dignity at work, on Article 26 of the revised Social Charter. The expression 'working conditions' is to be understood in the sense of Article 156 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union.

2. Paragraph 2 is based on Directive 93/104/EC concerning certain aspects of the organisation of working time, Article 2 of the European Social Charter and point 8 of the Community Charter on the rights of workers.'

Explanation on Article 32 (Prohibition of child labour and protection of young people at work):

'This Article is based on Directive 94/33/EC on the protection of young people at work, Article 7 of the European Social Charter and points 20 to 23 of the Community Charter of the Fundamental Social Rights of Workers.'

normative content of the fundamental right to occupational safety, health and dignity at work is also defined in the secondary EU legislation, including both framework Directive 89/391/EEC⁸ and individual directives⁹, and in the European Social Charter¹⁰ and the revised Social Charter¹¹. The combination of these sources suggests the application, among others, of the “consensual method”¹² of legal interpretation.

The connection between the directives and the fundamental rights established by the Charter is important. Namely, the provisions of the Charter are addressed to the member states only when they are implementing EU law.¹³ It is therefore legally relevant to consider the relationship of the Charter and the regulations passed in Croatia for the purpose of transposing into national legislation the requirements of directives on the protection of health, safety and dignity at work, because it concerns the implementation of EU legislation in a member state.

In order to understand the right of workers to the protection of dignity at work, it is important to implement Article 26 of the European Social Charter (revised), which reads: “With a view to ensuring the effective exercise of the right of all workers to protection of their dignity at work, the Parties undertake, in consultation with employers’ and workers’ organisations: to promote awareness, information and prevention of sexual harassment in the workplace or in relation to work and to take all appropriate measures to protect workers from such conduct; to promote awareness, information and prevention of recur-

Explanation on Article 34(1) (Social security and social assistance):

‘The principle set out in Article 34(1) is based on Articles 153 and 156 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Article 12 of the European Social Charter and point 10 of the Community Charter on the rights of workers. The Union must respect it when exercising the powers conferred on it by Articles 153 and 156 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. The reference to social services relates to cases in which such services have been introduced to provide certain advantages but does not imply that such services must be created where they do not exist. ‘Maternity’ must be understood in the same sense as in the preceding Article.’

⁸ Council Directive 89/391/EEC of 12 June 1989 on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health of workers at work (OJ L 183)

⁹ Updated overview of directives in force can be found in the EUR-Lex base in the registry area 05.20.20.10 Health and Safety, http://eur-lex.europa.eu/search.html?CC_1_CODED=05&CC_4_CODED=05202010&name=browse-by:legislation-in-force&CC_2_CODED=0520&displayProfile=allRelAll-ConsDocProfile&qid=1427211746387&CC_3_CODED=052020&type=named, (accessed 27 June 2015).

¹⁰ European Social Charter, CETS No. 35, <http://conventions.coe.int/Treaty/Commun/QueVoulezVous.asp?NT=035&CM=8&DF=05/06/2015&CL=ENG>, (accessed 27 June 2015).

¹¹ European Social Charter (revised), CETS No. 163, <http://conventions.coe.int/Treaty/Commun/QueVoulezVous.asp?NT=163&CM=8&DF=05/06/2015&CL=ENG>, (accessed 27 June 2015).

¹² C. Pitea, ‘Interpreting the ECHR in the Light of ‘Other Instruments’: Systemic Integration or Fragmentation of Rules on Treaty Interpretation?’, in N. Boschiero, T. Scovazzi, C. Pitea and C. Ragni (eds.), *International Courts and the Development of International Law, Essays in Honor of Prof. Tullio*, The Hague, Asser Press, 2013, p. 555.

¹³ Article 51 paragraph 1.

rent reprehensible or distinctly negative and offensive actions directed against individual workers in the workplace or in relation to work and to take all appropriate measures to protect workers from such conduct.”

With regard to connecting health, safety and dignity at work into a single right, which is a component part of the European concept of working conditions, it is of use to indicate that this concerns the rights of personality. According to Radolović, the right of personality is in the subjective sense “the right of a certain legal subject to seek from all other subjects and to enforce the respect and development of one’s own personality in accordance with one’s stage of psycho-social development. The stipulation is made towards the third parties, including the state, because the state is very frequently not only the infringer of someone’s subjective right of personality but also the promotor of the situations that create an unfavourable social environment regarding the development and enforcement of the right of personality. The state, however, is the only one that can present the other decisive factor for the proper development of this right.”¹⁴ Resulting from Radolović’s consideration of the role of the state, attention is drawn to the fact that the right to the protection of health and safety at work was recognized on the international level already in 1976 by way of entry into force of the Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights.¹⁵ Croatia is a party to the Covenant based on the notification of succession. The implementation of the Covenant is directed by the Maastricht Guidelines on Violations of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights¹⁶, which give instructions on the meaning of these rights, possibilities of violating them by conduct or omission, liability for violations and the right of individuals to effective state-guaranteed remedies for the protection of violated rights. According to the Guidelines, there are three different obligations imposed on states: to respect, to protect and to fulfil the rights. Failure to perform any one of these three obligations constitutes a violation of such rights. The obligation to respect requires states to refrain from interfering with the enjoyment of economic, social and cultural rights. The obligation to protect requires states to prevent violations of such rights by third parties. The obligation to fulfil requires states to take appropriate legislative, administrative, budgetary, judicial and other measures towards the full realization of such rights.

Consequent to the said facts, it should not be disputable that the right of workers in Croatia to occupational health, safety and dignity is a fundamental right in connection to which the state is obliged to ensure effective realization and protection. However, the effectiveness of realization and protection of the right depends on the precision by which

¹⁴ Author’s translation of the quote according to the following reference: A. Radolović, ‘Pravo osobnosti u novom Zakonu o obveznim odnosima’, *Zbornik Pravnog fakulteta Sveučilišta u Rijeci*, Vol. 27, No. 1, 2006, p. 133.

¹⁵ International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, United Nations: Human Rights, <http://www.ohchr.org/EN/ProfessionalInterest/Pages/CESCR.aspx>, (accessed 27 June 2015).

¹⁶ The Maastricht Guidelines on Violations of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, <http://www.unhcr.ch/tbs/doc.nsf/0/6b748989d76d2bb8c125699700500e17?Opendocument>, (accessed 27 June 2015).

the normative content of the right was regulated. With respect to the rights of workers following from the EU legal order, the realization and protection of the right may depend, in addition to the already mentioned factors, on the possibility for workers in Croatia to directly refer to that right before the courts or e.g. work inspectors during inspections. Of course, this is important in cases when Croatia partly or completely failed to transpose a certain labour-relations right into the national legal order.

Considering Article 51 of the Charter, Leczykiewicz thinks it is possible to refer to the Charter directly “where there exists an EU Directive which protects the relevant right but it has not been correctly implemented by the Member State. Absence of correct implementation can consist of situations where incompatible domestic provisions are preserved, the provisions adopted to implement the Directive do not adequately achieve the Directive’s objective, or national law is simply silent on the matter. Here the Charter could be used to make the right effective despite absence of correct implementation of the Directive.”¹⁷

2.2. Croatian legal framework

The Constitution of the Republic of Croatia¹⁸ defines the right of specific groups of employees (mothers, young people and disabled persons) to special protection at work. *Argumentum a contrario* – all other employees have the constitutional right to regular safety at work. Also, each employee shall under the Constitution be entitled to annual holidays with pay, and shall never waive these rights.

The Labour Act¹⁹ and the Occupational Health and Safety Act²⁰, as well as subordinate legislation, define the general normative content of the right to occupational safety and health. Special acts and other regulations additionally regulate that right specifically for workers in certain fields of activity (all types of traffic, humanitarian mine clearing, forestry, mining etc.). Directive 89/391/EEC is transposed by way of the Occupational Health and Safety Act, and individual directives by way of subordinate regulations. Directives on working time organization and special safety at work for minor workers are transposed by way of the Labour Act.

The Civil Obligations Act defines the rights of personality, which include the right to life, to physical and mental health, reputation, honour and dignity. Every person has the

¹⁷ D. Leczykiewicz, ‘Horizontal Application of the Charter of Fundamental Rights’, *European Law Review*, no. 38, available at <http://ssrn.com/abstract=2328175> (accessed 27 June 2015).

¹⁸ Ustav Republike Hrvatske, *eng.* Constitution of the Republic of Croatia (Official Gazette 56/90, 135/97, 113/00, 28/01, 76/10 and 5/14)

¹⁹ Zakon o radu, *eng.* Labour Act (Official Gazette 93/14)

²⁰ Zakon o zaštiti na radu, *eng.* Occupational Health and Safety Act (Official Gazette 71/14, 118/14, 154/14)

right to the protection of personality rights under the legally defined conditions.²¹ Naturally, the term “every person” applies also to every worker in Croatia.

The Anti-Discrimination Act²² regulates protection from harassment pursuant to the EU Directives that are by way of this Act transposed into the national legal order.²³

Croatia has signed but not yet ratified the revised Social Charter. Still, pursuant to the Explanations Relating to the Charter of Fundamental Rights, Croatia must apply the definition and normative content of the workers’ right to the protection of dignity as defined in Article 26 of the revised Social Charter (to promote awareness, information and prevention and to protect workers). There is obvious similarity of approaches found in The Explanations Relating to the Charter and the Maastricht Guidelines (to respect, to protect and to fulfil).

III. SELECTED EXAMPLES FROM REGULATIONS AND COURT PRACTICE IN CROATIA

3.1. Jobs performed under special working conditions

Jobs performed under special working conditions may be performed exclusively by employees fulfilling special prescribed conditions when performing these jobs. The purpose of this is to prevent harmful influences of work on the life and health of workers (injuries, professional diseases, other work-related diseases). Prescribed special conditions that workers must fulfil concern age, sex, professional abilities, health, physical and psychological condition (health status) and psychophysiological and psychological abilities (psychological fitness) of the candidates for employment or the workers performing certain jobs. Within the framework of special conditions of health status and psychological fitness, contraindication is prescribed. The employer must check whether the employee fulfils special conditions prior to employment, and during employment the employer must ensure in the given periods of time that periodic controls of complying with the special conditions for the performance of jobs are carried out. On the occasion of repeated check-up of health status and psychological fitness, it is determined whether the

²¹ Article 19 of the Zakon o obveznim odnosima, *eng.* Civil Obligations Act (Official Gazette 35/05, 41/08 and 125/11)

²² Zakon o suzbijanju diskriminacije, *eng.* Anti-Discrimination Act (Official Gazette 85/08 and 112/12)

²³ Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation (OJ L 303, 02. 12. 2000.); Council Directive 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin (OJ L 180, 19. 7. 2000.); Council Directive 2004/113/EC of 13 December 2004 implementing the principle of equal treatment between men and women in the access to and supply of goods and services (OJ C 373, 21. 12. 2004.); Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast) (OJ L 204, 26. 07. 2006.)

worker has experienced any health damage or changes of psychological status which are prescribed as contraindications for job performance, or whether there has been deviation concerning prescribed conditions. Health status and psychological fitness needed for the continuation of work are evaluated depending on the level of the possible damage of health or changes in the psychological condition of the worker. The evaluation is provided by the specialist in occupational medicine who the employer engages to provide this service to the workers. If there are any changes diagnosed, the employer must urgently apply additional measures for the protection of workers' health and safety. The employer must not hire a new employee unless all prescribed conditions regarding the health status and psychological fitness are met. Likewise, the employer must not allow the worker to continue performing jobs under special working conditions if it is determined during a periodic check-up that he or she no longer meets all prescribed conditions. The worker may demand an *ad hoc* check-up even prior to the regular periodic check-up time.

There are in total 56 jobs recognized as the jobs performed under special working conditions, including for example those of firefighter and diver, then the jobs including the exposure of the worker to vibrations, chemical or biological agents, the jobs demanding heavy physical strain, the jobs performed at heights or in unfavourable microclimate, the jobs of protecting persons and property that include firearms and many other.²⁴ The list is open-ended, allowing the employer to determine that in his or her case there are other jobs that are performed under special working conditions in addition to the ones listed under 56 prescribed jobs. Preventive measures, dynamics of health status and psychological fitness check-ups and employer's obligations are drawn up based on the assumption that a worker performs a job under special working conditions full time (40 hours per week). If the worker works within the framework of full time hours and if the employer implements all prescribed obligations i.e. preventive measures, the health status and psychological fitness of workers performing jobs under special working conditions should not change to the detriment of workers.

However, in 2014 the Labour Act defined a new right of workers. Now the Labour Act allows an employee with a full-time employment to conclude a labour contract with another employer, with the maximum duration of eight hours a week, or 180 hours a year. An employee must for this purpose obtain the consent of the primary employer in writing.²⁵ By introducing this provision into the Labour Act, the legislator had in mind primarily its effects on the labour market demand and supply, completely disregarding the connection with the regulations on occupational safety and health. When the provisions of the Labour Act are looked at from the perspective of the Occupational Health and Safety Act, it is clear that there is lacking normative content and a wide field of insecurity regarding the fundamental

²⁴ Pravilnik o poslovima s posebnim uvjetima rada, *eng.* The Ordinance on Jobs Performed under Special Working Conditions (Official Gazette 5/84)

²⁵ Article 61 paragraph 3

right to occupational health and safety of workers performing jobs under special working conditions. The normative content of both workers' rights and employers' obligations and responsibilities has remained deficient in the said type of a cumulative employment status.

The subject of the provision of Article 61 paragraph 3 of the Labour Act is "a full-time worker". The provision refers to working time only, and not to working conditions such as e.g. special working conditions pursuant to the Ordinance on Jobs Performed under Special Working Conditions. The regulations pertaining to labour law in Croatia provide no answer to the question whether an employer may allow an employee performing 40-hours-week job under special working conditions for him to perform higher-risk jobs for another employer. The second employer's risk assessment will not establish that the job performed for him entails higher risks, because the employee performs it only eight hours a week or not more than 180 hours a year. What if the employee in addition to 40 hours working for the primary employer performs for the same employer the job overtime and has regarding this provided his or her written consent to perform higher-risk jobs for another employer? Does the obligation and responsibility of the employer to undertake safety and health measures refer also to the employment of that worker with another employer? Is the employer for the reasons of occupational safety and health protection free to deny written consent to the worker and that way prevent him or her from concluding the other labour contract? Should the employer prior to giving consent be notified of the assessment of risk of performing the job for another employer? Or, should the other employer take into account the risks a worker is already exposed to while working full time? Should care be taken of possible effects on health status and psychological fitness that can be caused by the exposure of the worker to the combination of risks from both employments? Does the second employer have to arrange occupational medicine services for the worker he or she employs 180 hours a year and does he or she have to check the health status and psychological fitness of that worker? Does it suffice that only the first employer checks this? What if the opinions of occupational medicine specialists employed by both employers respectively differ? Does this give the right to the worker to seek an independent opinion of a third specialist and does this opinion then oblige both employers? Are only complicated expert evaluations of the health status and psychological fitness of the worker and of working conditions at both employers able to suggest the final conclusion as to which employment reduces the working ability of the worker, should there appear such reduction? A barrage of questions we need to face here is obvious, because the questions are not merely hypothetical but have direct consequences for both the realization of the fundamental right to occupational safety and health in every work-related way and the damages sought in case of any harm to health or reduction or loss of the working ability.

All the mentioned difficulties are fully relevant for every cumulative employment, including the cases in which the worker performing jobs under special working conditions works part-time cumulatively for two or more employers in order to reach full-time working hours.

There are too many unresolved questions and there is too much consequential legal uncertainty to allow the interpretation based on the appeal to the freedom to regulate obligations²⁶.

3.2. Dignity at work

Failure to care for the protection of the dignity of the worker directly implies the failure to care for the protection of health, because many forms of harassment and violence directly harm the health of the worker.²⁷

The Anti-Discrimination Act, which *inter alia* applies to the area of work and employment, provides protection in case of harassment, but exclusively in relation to the prohibited grounds of discrimination that apply in anti-discrimination legislation (race or ethnic affiliation or colour, gender, language, religion, political or other belief, national or social origin, property, trade union membership, education, social status, marital or family status, age, health condition, disability, genetic heritage, native identity, expression or sexual orientation).²⁸ The Act imposes no preventive measures that would oblige the employer. It only regulates the court protection of the victim of harassment, which is in case of workers carried out in a labour dispute.

The Labour Act regulates the employer's obligation to undertake measures against harassment, but only posterior to the event of harassment and upon the inspection of the worker's complaint, on the basis of which adequate measures are undertaken to prevent the continuation of harassment in an individual case.²⁹ These measures are not preventive, but present merely a reaction to already suffered harassment and they are not designed for the purposes of preventive protection of all workers, but for a specific reported case of harassment.

Hence, there is no obligatory preventive measure to be undertaken by the employer to protect the employee that follows from the two discussed pieces of legislation. Unfortunately, it does not follow from the third act as well. Namely, in the process of passing

²⁶ Article 8 paragraph 4 of the Labour Act and article 2 of the Civil Obligations Act.

²⁷ The conclusion is justified by the research results e.g. S. Einarsen and M. Birkeland Nielsen, 'Workplace bullying as an antecedent of mental health problems: a five-year prospective and representative study', *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, Vol. 88, No. 2, 2015, pp. 131 – 142.; C.C. Rodríguez et al., 'Workplace Harassment and Workers' Health: Review of the 'Mobbing and Health' Working Groups', *Social Medicine*, Vol. 6, No. 4, 2012, pp. 266 – 267, <http://www.socialmedicine.info/index.php/socialmedicine/article/view/640/1245>, (accessed 27. 06. 2015.); Jagdish Khubchandani and James H. Price, 'Workplace Harassment and Morbidity Among US Adults: Results from the National Health Interview Survey', *Journal of Community Health*, No. 40, 2015, <http://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10900-014-9971-2#page-1>, (accessed 27 June 2015.)

²⁸ Article 1 paragraph 1 and article 3 paragraph 3

²⁹ Article 134

the new Occupational Health and Safety Act, all the provisions designed to contribute in a general preventive sense to the prevention, recognition and resolving of the problem of harassment at work or related to work have been removed from the text of the bill. With the participation of social partners, an unacceptable inconsistency has been made legal. As a result, regarding alcohol intoxication at work, the employer explicitly prescribes preventive measures to be taken by the employer that are considered adequate. Pursuant to the same legislation, however, in case of harassment at work or related to work, the legislator mentions no preventive measure or the obligation of the employer to implement it.

Contrary to this, Directive 89/391/EEC stipulates the employer's obligations to assess all work-related risks and to protect the worker from them in a preventive rather than reactive manner.³⁰ Hence, two obligations are prescribed: to assess risks in all work-related ways and protect the worker from the determined risks. Necessary quality or effectiveness of protection is also prescribed ("... the preventive measures and the working and production methods implemented by the employer must assure an improvement in the level of protection afforded to workers with regard to safety and health and be integrated into all the activities of the undertaking and/or establishment and at all hierarchical levels; ..."). The protection is provided based on the general principles of prevention. In this case there are three important principles (avoiding risks, evaluating the risks which cannot be avoided, combating the risks at source).³¹ The accent is clearly put on the primary prevention, thus suggesting the conclusion that Croatian regulations that only determine the right of the victim of harassment to court protection are far from meeting EU legal requirements concerning preventive action aimed at preventing harmful consequences of harassment at work or related to work. Specifically, according to the current regulations in Croatia, the employer cannot be held responsible for failing to take a particular preventive measure or be commanded to take it, and the worker cannot be confident about the content of the right to protection that should be provided to him by the employer or seek from the employer particular preventive actions. The worker can refer to his or her legal rights and undertake protection only posterior to becoming the victim of harassment, because it is only then that the worker falls within the scope of the provisions of the Labour Act.

It is a belief wrongly held in Croatia that harassment at work appears exclusively in relation to the forbidden bases of discrimination prescribed in corresponding EU Directives and that the legislator has completely regulated all issues related to harassment of workers at work or in relation to work once the requirements pronounced in these directives have been transposed to the national legal order by way of the Anti-Discrimination Act. Quite

³⁰ Article 5 paragraph 1: '1. The employer shall have a duty to ensure the safety and health of workers in every aspect related to the work.'

Article 6 paragraph 3 (a): '3. Without prejudice to the other provisions of this Directive, the employer shall, taking into account the nature of the activities of the enterprise and / or establishment: (a) evaluate the risks to the safety and health of workers...'

³¹ Article 6 paragraph 2 (a), (b), (c)

the contrary, there are many cases of harassment at work not in any way connected with discrimination. An example can be the harassment related to the hierarchical position of the person who harasses (so called *bossing*). Another example is the harassment of teachers by students. It does not have to be connected with any of the forbidden bases of discrimination, but is simply an inappropriate, humiliating and unacceptable reaction of students to the decisions made by teachers when they apply the criteria for student achievement evaluation.

European social partners have recognized harassment and violence as work-related risks that may affect every workplace and every worker, regardless of the company size, field of activity or the form of the work contract or labour relations. More importantly, they have become aware that certain groups and branches of activity are under greater safety risks, and pursuant to these conclusions they have entered into the European framework agreement on harassment and violence at work³², which mentions direct connection with Directive 89/391/EEC. It has also been recognized by the European Commission.³³ Hence, it is not disputed in the least that EU regulations pertaining to occupational safety and health refer to and should be applied to the harassment as a risk at work or related to work, particularly framework Directive 89/391/EEC, in all cases when harassment is not related to the forbidden bases of discrimination. Regulations in Croatia should reflect this, taking care to oblige the institutions that bring forward, pass and implement regulations.

Social partners in Croatia obviously cannot support the role of European social partners and take responsibility for enforcing the Framework Agreement. This was proven during their participation in the public discussion on the draft of the Occupational Health and Safety Act. It is therefore not realistic to expect that a collective agreement might be a legal source for compensating the discussed failures of the legislator in Croatia related to the regulation of the protection of dignity of workers at work or related to work. The state should completely fulfil its duty, because the obligations follow from EU Directives, and the directives are legal instruments addressed by the EU to its member states.

3.3. Work under the influence of alcohol

The presented two examples indicate that the failures of the legislator to precisely determine the normative content of a particular right contribute to legal security, realistic expectations of addressees and legal effectiveness. Legal security and effectiveness are

³² European framework agreement on harassment and violence at work, Brussels, <http://www.etuc.org/framework-agreement-harassment-and-violence-work>, (accessed 27 June 2015).

³³ Commission of the European Communities. 'Communication from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament transmitting the European framework agreement on harassment and violence at work', COM(2007) 686 final, Brussels, p. 4, http://www.europarl.europa.eu/hearings/20071121/femm/framework_agreement_en.pdf, (accessed 27 June 2015.)

constitutional categories in the framework of the rule of law. Realistic expectations of addressees, in this case the workers in Croatia, result from the EU legal order, which guarantees the fundamental right of workers to the protection of health, safety and dignity at work and related to work.

The purpose of the following example is to draw attention to the fact that it is sometimes in Croatia the case that even completely correct normative content of a particular right cannot help workers protect their fundamental right to the protection of health, safety and dignity at work. This refers to the situations in which the way institutions enforce the law contributes to legal insecurity or even illegal decision-making. The problems are in this manner generated in a new, unexpected and completely unjustified way, reversing thereby all the benefits of appropriate legislation.

The Occupational Health and Safety Act prohibits work under the influence of alcohol, whereby the procedure to check whether the worker is under the influence of alcohol is specified. Under the established procedure, the use of alcotest, breath test or other suitable device or means is foreseen.³⁴ The courts in Croatia have in the last twenty years consistently passed rulings that the termination of the labour contract on account of alcohol intoxication of the worker is unauthorised if it is not determined by alcotest but only based on depositions of other workers as witnesses. Legal opinion of the courts in such a case is that alcohol intoxication has not been proven.³⁵

³⁴ Article 59 paragraph 1.

³⁵ The following rulings and legal interpretations contained in them serve as examples (author's translation):

‘Alcohol intoxication of workers cannot be determined by way of witnesses’ depositions.’, Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske, *eng.* Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia, Rev 2873/99.

‘Alcohol intoxication of workers should be determined by means of an alcotest or other suitable instrument or tool, and only exceptionally, when no suitable instruments are at the employer's disposal, can alcohol intoxication be determined in some other way if the fact of intoxication during the very event was not in question. For example, such case would be when the worker admitted it him/herself or when it results from the worker's conduct that he/she admits the consumption of alcohol and being influenced by it.’, Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske, *eng.* Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia, Revr 2077/00.

‘In determining alcohol intoxication of the plaintiff, the defendant failed to use alcotest or some other device... The plaintiff agreed to the test of alcohol intoxication. If alcohol intoxication of the plaintiff were determined in a way other than the one defined in Article 65 of the Occupational Health and Safety Act, according to the proper assessment of the courts, the defendant failed to prove in any of the ways the claim about the plaintiff's alcohol intoxication. The circumstance that the plaintiff was treated for alcoholism does not per se influence the conclusion that the plaintiff in the disputed case was under the influence of alcohol. Given the fact that there is no evidence of the plaintiff in the disputed case being under the influence of alcohol, the courts commanded the defendant to reemploy the plaintiff as salesman-shift manager at a petrol station.’, Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske, *eng.* Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia, Revr 267/07-2.

‘In terms of the provision of Article 65 of the Occupational Health and Safety Act, the employer is obliged to temporarily remove from the workplace the worker under the influence of alcohol, and alcohol intoxication i.e. the presence of alcohol in the organism can be determined by alcotest or other suitable device or procedure, and if the worker refuses the testing, he is considered to be under the influence of alcohol. The defendant in the given case failed to act in accordance with this legal provision, because he failed to determine the plaintiff's alcohol intoxication in the prescribed way. The defendant wrongly thinks that in

However, the Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia revises the ruling³⁶ to allow the termination of the work contract and deems it possible to establish alcohol intoxication based on “the experiential estimation of witnesses” (supports the ruling of the court of first instance). The court of second instance established in this case that pursuant to the Occupational Health and Safety Act³⁷ alcohol intoxication of the worker remained unproven, because it is allowed to determine intoxication exclusively by means of alcotest, which was not the case. Evident departure from legal provisions was defended by the Supreme Court on the grounds that the failure of the employer to administer the alcotest was the reason of organizational nature (working hours of persons in charge of administering the alcotest were over), and that this must not be the reason for leaving the worker unsanctioned for alcohol intoxication. The Supreme Court contradicts with the presented interpretation not only legal provisions concerning the way to check alcohol intoxication of the worker but also legal regulations concerning obligations and responsibilities of the employer to organize the implementation of preventive and organizational measures for the protection of health and safety of the worker, the organization of occupational safety service included. The employer must not organize the work of occupational safety service in such a way that after the working hours of the service, and during working hours of other employees, there is no one with access to alcotest or without the presence of at least one worker qualified for the proper use of alcotest. The employer who failed to meet legal requirements is according to this ruling enabled to terminate the labour contract of the worker whose intoxication has not been proven, and by reason of the employer’s own organizational oversight.

The ruling also lays foundation for the wrong interpretation of the right of the employer to prohibit the worker from working, and in relation to the termination of the employment contract. Namely, according to the Occupational Health and Safety Act the

the given case he could not perform the testing for alcohol intoxication of the plaintiff. The circumstance that some passengers thought the plaintiff was under the influence of alcohol on that occasion is no proof of the plaintiff’s alcoholisation.’, Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske, *eng.* Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia, Revr 626/08-2.

‘Not every case of alcohol intoxication is the reason for irregular termination of the employment contract, but only the case that would present a particularly severe violation of the obligations defined in the employment contract and that would render the continuation of the worker’s employment by the same employer impossible. The courts ruled that the plaintiff is a good worker, that there were no alcohol-related problems at work in this case, that he is ill and that he has 33 years of employment. The courts rightly held that legal presumptions for the irregular termination of the employment contract were not fulfilled.’, Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske, *eng.* Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia, Revr 312/12-2

³⁶ Vrhovni sud Republike Hrvatske, *eng.* Supreme Court of the Republic of Croatia, Revr 1074/09-2.

³⁷ The ruling is based on the 1996 version of the Occupational Health and Safety Act, which is no longer in force. All the facts specified in this example are completely relevant for the enforcement of the current Occupational Health and Safety Act (passed in 2014), as well as of the 1996 Act. Namely, the provisions of the new act on obligations of employers related to the work of workers under the influence of alcohol and to the organization of the implementation of occupational safety measures are identical to the 1996 provisions.

employer must prohibit the worker under the influence of alcohol from working, but it is not obligatory in that case to terminate the employment contract. The connection between prohibition to work and termination of the employment contract is established in the Labour Act, but the Occupational Health and Safety Act has a priority in application, because it presents specialized legislation. Pursuant to the Occupational Health and Safety Act, prohibition to work is a preventive organizational measure for the protection of health and safety of workers. When there is indication that the worker is under the influence of alcohol, the employer should as a measure of precaution prohibit him from working and may do it based on the indication. However, the termination of the employment contract cannot be based upon indication but exclusively on evidence, which is alcohol intoxication determined in a legally prescribed way.

A ruling that would repeat the said debatable legal interpretations should not be issued before Croatian courts ever again, just as the discussed one should not have ever been issued. Namely, the legal provision relating to the way of determining alcohol intoxication of workers while working is clear to the extent to which it does not require court explanations, especially not elaborate to the extent that they negate the legal right of the worker to have alcohol intoxication tested exclusively by means of prescribed technical devices and procedures. Also, Directive 89/391/EEC, as well as the Occupational Health and Safety Act (both 2014 and 1996) indisputably define the employer as responsible for the organization of and resources for occupational safety. In addition to this, it is important that the Occupational Health and Safety Act defines misdemeanour liability of the employer in cases of failing to implement by way of appropriate measures the prohibition of misusing alcoholic beverages at workplace.³⁸ The legal list of appropriate measures contains, among others, the obligation of the employer to define in writing and effectively implement the procedure of testing whether a worker is under the influence of alcohol. The procedure includes the worker's consent, the method of testing, the type of test or devices, recording methods and methods for verification of results, the procedure in the event that an employee refuses to be subjected to testing. Hence, the depositions of witnesses are in no way legally relevant or encompassed by prescribed measures. Finally, but not less importantly, there is a legal obligation of the employer i.e. the authorized occupational safety officer to prohibit the workers under the influence of alcohol from working and to instruct them to leave the workplace, whereby the employer is obliged to ensure the entrusted person the conditions for the realization of that authority.³⁹ This includes ensuring the availability of instruments for testing alcohol intoxication and the services of a person trained to perform that procedure, or otherwise the authorized person must be trained to perform the testing in a regular way in order to be able to test alcohol intoxication of workers in a legal way. All specified obligations and responsibilities of the employer were defined un-

³⁸ Articles 95 and 58

³⁹ Article 24

der the 1996 Occupational Health and Safety Act. Still, the illustrated questionable ruling shows that they were completely disregarded by the Supreme Court. Provisions with clear normative content were unnecessarily interpreted, to the detriment of workers and so extensively that they eventually departed from the legal provisions stipulating important obligations of employers.

IV. CONCLUSION

Many more examples like the ones described above could be listed. They would all lead to the same conclusion. It is either the regulations or the institutions in charge of their implementation that fail. The consequences are suffered by the workers, because they are left with long-lasting and uncertain legal proceeding concerning the protection of their work-related rights.

Unquestionable oversights in general labour law result from the uncoordinated and thus improper division of jurisdiction between the Labour Act and the Occupational Health and Safety Act. The consequence is that important questions concerning the protection of safety and health and dignity of workers are generally not regulated, and the solutions from special legislation provide no assistance as well. Whenever and however the main actors of these processes decide to change the provisions concerning working hours and rest, they only have the effects on the labour market in mind, completely thereby disregarding the fact that they interfere with special provisions the fundamental purpose of which is to protect the health, safety and dignity of workers. The rules regarding the organization of working hours and rests belong to special rules of occupational safety and health in the EU legislation, and this is what they must be in the national juridical system as well. The right to the protection of health, occupational safety and dignity is the fundamental right of workers in the EU, and thereby of workers in Croatia as well.

Also, it is necessary to finally start consistently applying regulations concerning the regulatory impact assessment, for the purpose of realizing the objectives they are designed for (*SMART regulations* – standardised, measurable, actionable, reliable, transparent). The decision to, for example, skip important parts of the procedure in the preparation of the draft of the act significantly shortens the periods of public discussion with experts, engages too much politics, leads to insufficient or no expert consultation, and produces inconsistent legislation that cannot efficiently protect the subjective rights of workers.

Transferring the burden from legislator to courts is of no help. Namely, if the parties in a labour dispute appeal to the EU law, this form of protection is significantly slowed down, because there is an obligation of national courts to pose prior questions to the Court of Justice of the European Union concerning interpretations of the EU legislation. That preliminary procedure is almost impossible to avoid, because the major part of the labour

law in Croatia has originated from EU law i.e. from the requirement to align national legislation with that of the EU.

Lastly, in addition to workers, damage is suffered also by tax payers, because they have to finance the administration which is excessive precisely due to the inefficiency of the juridical system. SMART regulation would decrease the need for intervention of work inspectors, courts, arbitration and other institutions.